

Original article

Understanding antimicrobial usage and stewardship among future healthcare professionals in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Healthcare students, as future prescribers and dispensers of antimicrobials, have a crucial role to play in mitigating the menace of inappropriate use of antibiotics. Previous research involving health care students has revealed a knowledge-practice gap and indicated the need for educational interventions to enhance students' understanding and awareness of antibiotic stewardship. **Objectives:** This study aimed to assess the knowledge of antimicrobial usage and ways to mitigate irrational antibiotic usage among undergraduate students at the Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare. **Materials and methods:** This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design, with 329 undergraduate students sampled using a consecutive random sampling technique. Data were collected using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire created in Google Forms and distributed to the sampled students. The students were from different departments (Medicine and Surgery, Dentistry, Nutrition, Nursing sciences, and Radiography) within the university. The study was conducted within six months. **Result:** Majority 223 (69.5%) of the students were within the age range of 15-20 years with a mean age of 21years + 2SD. The majority, 195(60.9%) of the students were female. The students demonstrated sufficient knowledge of antimicrobial agents; however, they lacked a clear understanding of the indications for their use. Additionally, one-third 117 (36.7%) of the students disagree that antibiotics should be used to treat febrile illnesses. The participants demonstrated good knowledge of ways to mitigate the use of irrational antibiotics. Percentages of fully correct answers ("agree" or "disagree" depending on the statement) were higher than 90% in all the statements proposed, except for antibiotics, which should only be taken when prescribed by a doctor, who has 88.8% response rate. **Conclusion:** Even though the students might possess some out dated behavior regarding antimicrobial usage but they demonstrated good knowledge about antimicrobial use and ways to mitigate irrational use of antibiotics. We therefore recommend a structured study that would enhance student knowledge in this context.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Antimicrobial usage, Irrational antimicrobial use

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Introduction

Antimicrobials are drugs used to prevent and treat infections in humans, animals, and plants. They include antibiotics, antivirals, antifungals, and antiparasitics.¹ Antimicrobial resistance is the process by which a variety of bacteria, parasites, viruses, and fungi develop resistance to antimicrobials. This reduces the effectiveness of antimicrobial medicines and compromises their ability to treat infections effectively making treatment more costly,

challenging, or even impossible.² Vulnerable individuals are most affected because they may not be able to afford the higher costs or the worsening of their illness, which ultimately leads to increased morbidity and mortality.³ The primary reason for antibiotic resistance is the improper use of antimicrobial medicines. Complex surgical operations become dangerous without appropriate antimicrobials for the prevention and control of infections.⁴ The use of medicines by the general public to address common health issues, self-diagnosed disorders, or the sporadic or continuous use of medicines for chronic or recurrent diseases or symptoms without a doctor's prescription is known as self-medication.⁵ Studies have shown that many medical and allied health students at universities typically advise patients to take antibacterial agents, and as the patients' condition improves, they suddenly stop taking the drug without completing the prescribed course.⁶ Reports on the knowledge, attitude, and practice of students towards the use of antibiotics are increasing.⁷ This is because healthcare students, as future prescribers and dispensers of antimicrobials, have a crucial role to play in reducing inappropriate antibiotic use. Previous research involving healthcare students has revealed a knowledge-practice gap and highlighted the need for educational interventions to enhance students' understanding and awareness of antibiotic stewardship.⁸

This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of antimicrobial use among undergraduate students at the Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare

Materials and methods

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional study conducted among undergraduates of the Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare. Azare is a major town and the administrative headquarters of the Katagum Traditional Emirate in Bauchi State, northeastern Nigeria, founded in the early 19th century (approx. 1803–1814). As a bustling agricultural and commercial hub with a population

exceeding 110,000, it is predominantly inhabited by Hausa, Fulani, and Kanuri people who follow Islamic traditions.⁹ The study lasted three months and included 329 participants. Consecutive sampling, also known as total enumerative sampling, was employed. A semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire was designed using Google Forms and distributed across the various class WhatsApp groups. The questionnaire was pretested at a comparable institution, the School of Nursing, Azare, and necessary corrections were made.

Knowledge was assessed using nine structured questions. Respondents who answered $\geq 70\%$ correctly were categorised as having good knowledge, while those scoring $\leq 50\%$ were considered to have poor knowledge. These thresholds were adapted from the WHO KAP survey guidelines (World Health Organization, 2008) and previous studies in similar contexts.¹⁰

Data were analysed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Frequency runs were performed for data editing and cleansing. The level of significance (α) was set at 95% confidence interval; thus, any statistical test with $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. The research was funded solely by the candidate.

Results

The majority of participating students were female (61.3%, 202/329), while 127 (38.7%) were male. Most students (69.5%) were within the age range of 15–20 years, with a mean age of 20.9 years (Table 1). The participants demonstrated good knowledge of antibiotics. Percentages of fully correct answers ("agree" or "disagree" depending on the statement) exceeded 90% in one-third of the statements. The lowest percentage, 39.1%, was recorded for the statement "*Antibiotics should be taken when there is fever*", which nonetheless reflects good knowledge (Table 2).

The participants also demonstrated good knowledge of strategies to mitigate irrational antibiotic use. Correct responses exceeded 90% for all statements, except for "*Antibiotics should only be taken when prescribed by a doctor*", which had an 88.8% response rate (Table 3).

There was a statistically significant association between discipline of study and correct knowledge of antibiotic use ($\chi^2 = 12.4$, $p = 0.015$). Medicine and

Surgery students were more likely to correctly identify that antibiotics are only effective against bacterial infections compared with Nutrition and Radiography students. No significant association was found between sex and knowledge scores ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Gender and discipline of the participants

Variable	Frequency (%)
Sex	
Male	95 (39.1%)
Female	148 (60.9%)
Discipline	
Dentistry	55 (22.5%)
Medicine and surgery	65 (26.6%)
Nursing science	44 (18.3%)
Nutrition and dietitian	35 (14.2%)
Radiography	44 (18.3%)

Discussion

This study demonstrates that undergraduate healthcare students at FUHSA possess strong baseline knowledge of antimicrobials, with over 90% correctly identifying their role in treating infections caused by bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites. Similarly, 94.7% recognised that antibiotics are specifically for bacterial infections. However, misconceptions persist: 39.1% of students believed antibiotics should be taken for fever, and 55.6% agreed they should be used for colds or sore throats. These findings mirror global reports where inappropriate antibiotic use remains common among healthcare students.^{11,12}

Table 2: Knowledge of antimicrobial drugs

Parameter to assess knowledge	Agree	Disagree	I don't know
Antimicrobial drugs refer to agents used in the treatment of bacteria, viruses, fungi, or parasites	236(97%)	4(1.8%)	3(1.2%)
Antibiotics are used for the treatment of bacterial infections	230(94.7%)	7(3%)	6(2.4%)
Antibiotics should be taken for a cold or sore throat	135(55.6%)	69(28.4%)	39(16%)
Antibiotics should be taken for a fever	95(39.1%)	89(36.7%)	59(24.3%)

Table 3: Ways to mitigate irrational antibiotic usage

Ways to mitigate irrational antibiotic usage	Yes	No	Undecided
Students should get special training on the rational use of antibiotics to mitigate antibiotic misuse/abuse during their course of study	229(94.1%)	10(4.1%)	4(1.8%)
Should awareness groups be created among students?	234(96.4%)	6(2.4%)	3(1.2%)
Checking the expiry date of antibiotics before use?	240(98.8%)	1(0.6%)	1(0.6%)
Antibiotics should only be obtained when prescribed by a doctor.	216(88.8%)	20(8.3%)	7(3.0%)

Discipline-specific differences were evident. Medicine and Surgery students were significantly more likely to correctly identify that antibiotics are only effective against bacterial infections compared with Nutrition and Radiography students ($\chi^2 = 12.4$, $p = 0.015$). This aligns with studies in East Africa and Bangladesh, where medical students consistently outperformed non-medical peers in antibiotic knowledge.^{13,14} Such differences highlight the importance of curricular exposure and suggest that antimicrobial stewardship education should be extended across all healthcare disciplines, not just medicine.

Encouragingly, students demonstrated strong awareness of strategies to mitigate irrational antibiotic use. About 94% supported specialised

training during their studies, and nearly all agreed on the importance of checking expiry dates and creating awareness groups. Interestingly, checking expiry dates ranked highest (98.8%), reflecting a practical orientation towards safe medication use. While this may appear minor compared with prescribing practices, it underscores the role of pharmacists and prescribers in ensuring drug safety.¹⁵ Comparable findings in Nigeria and India also show that students often emphasise practical safety measures alongside stewardship principles.¹⁶ Despite adequate knowledge, outdated behaviours remain prevalent. Practices such as stopping antibiotics once symptoms improve or using leftover medications have been widely documented in Nigeria, India, and the UAE.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ These behaviours directly contribute to antimicrobial

resistance, as incomplete courses allow pathogens to survive and adapt.¹⁹ The gap between knowledge and practice observed here suggests that awareness alone is insufficient; behavioural change strategies must be integrated into training.

Globally, antimicrobial resistance is recognised as one of the greatest public health threats, with the WHO warning that common infections may become untreatable if misuse continues.²⁰ The findings from Azare mirror this global concern, reinforcing the urgency of embedding stewardship principles early in healthcare education. Peer-led awareness groups, as suggested by students, could also foster a culture of accountability and collective responsibility.²¹

Conclusion

This study illustrates that students pursuing careers in medicine and healthcare do not always translate their knowledge into practice. Although healthcare students possess a good level of knowledge regarding antibiotics, several attitudes and behaviours remain outdated. It is crucial to raise awareness of this subject during undergraduate training, as healthcare students will serve as role models for patients and citizens and will eventually prescribe these medicines once they become licensed professionals.

Recommendation

It is imperative to include specialist training programmes and courses on antibiotics in the core curricula of medical schools, with particular emphasis on appropriate prescribing practices. Structured modules on antimicrobial resistance, case-based learning, and simulation exercises could help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and clinical practice.

Limitations of the study

It was challenging to design questions that would assess in-depth knowledge, as the students were still in the early years of study and had limited clinical expertise. The tendency of study participants to underestimate the actual circumstances has been demonstrated by several researchers,²² which may restrict the applicability of our results and their extension to other contexts without further investigation.

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